

Project Management Information System Tools and Performance of Mechanical Building Services in Construction Projects in Kiambu County, Kenya

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Abstract

This research is purposed to establish the influence of PMIS tools to the performance of mechanical building services in construction projects in Kiambu County in Kenya. The major cause of failure in building construction projects is lack of adoption of technology among those involved in Mechanical Building Services in construction. Developing countries have a high rate of lower project performance compared to developed countries. Project Management Information Systems (PMIS) tools are integral tools for efficient planning, execution, and monitoring of Mechanical building services in construction projects globally. However, despite their widespread adoption, the extent to which PMIS tools contribute to the overall performance of building construction projects is unclear. The study seeks to examine the influence of project management information system tools on performance of Mechanical Building Services in construction projects in Kiambu County, Kenya. The specific objectives that the study seeks to achieve are to examine the influence of quality of PMIS tools, PMIS tools information output status, utilization level of PMIS tools and PMIS tools software ability on the performance of Mechanical building services in construction projects in Kiambu County, Kenya. The study has adopted three theories; Theory of Constraints, Resource Based Theory and Systems Theory. The study has developed a conceptual framework to show the relationship between Project Information Management System tools and performance of Mechanical building services in construction projects in Kenya. The study will adopt a descriptive research design. The target population for the study will be engineers, architects, contractors and project managers. The data collection instrument will be a semi-structured questionnaire. A pilot study will be conducted to verify the validity and reliability of the data collection tools before actual data collection. Data analysis will be carried out using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Presentation of data will be in form of charts and tables as it will be deemed appropriate.

Keywords: *Project Management Information System Tools, Construction Projects, Mechanical Building Services.*

JEL Classification codes: *L74, O32, M11, M15, D24.*

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Introduction

Background Information

Project Management Information Systems (PMIS) are designed to support effective planning, monitoring, and execution of projects by organizing and analyzing project data. They enhance collaboration, scheduling, budgeting, communication, and risk management, enabling project managers to make informed decisions and avoid being overwhelmed by large volumes of information (Mitey, 2022; Obeidat & Aldulaimi, 2016). PMIS tools also assist in scope, cost, time, quality, and integration management while generating reports, charts, and performance analyses that can be shared with stakeholders (Akamah & Jackson, 2016). By tracking individual task costs and updating plans based on new data, PMIS improves budget accuracy and supports performance control throughout the project life cycle (Obeidat & Aldulaimi, 2016; Ongondo et al., 2019).

In construction projects, particularly in Mechanical Building Services (MBS), effective coordination is essential due to the complexity and interdependence of systems such as HVAC, water supply, and sanitary drainage. Mechanical building services are critical for ensuring comfort and functionality in buildings, and poor coordination can lead to delays, rework, and cost overruns (Ongondo et al., 2019). Building Information Modelling (BIM), a specialized PMIS tool in construction, enhances time, cost, and quality management by enabling 3D modelling, accurate material cost estimation, and improved sequencing of activities before the construction phase begins (Fotiou, 2022). Globally, BIM adoption is increasing, particularly in public sector projects, although implementation levels vary across regions (BIM Africa, 2020).

In Kenya, especially in Kiambu County, rapid growth in the construction sector has been accompanied by persistent challenges such as project delays, cost escalations, and inefficient coordination of Mechanical Building Services. Limited adoption of PMIS tools and inadequate real-time information sharing contribute significantly to these performance issues (BIM Africa, 2020). Although awareness of BIM is relatively high in Africa, actual implementation remains moderate, and knowledge gaps still exist (BIM Africa, 2020). There is therefore a need to examine how PMIS tools—focusing on software quality, information output, utilization levels, and system capabilities—influence project performance in terms of time, cost, quality, and client satisfaction in the Kenyan construction industry (Fotiou, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

The construction industry in Kenya continues to experience significant performance challenges, particularly in the management and coordination of Mechanical Building Services (MBS). Many projects are characterized by delays, cost overruns, and quality deficiencies, largely attributed to weak project management practices and poor integration of technological tools (Njau, 2019). Empirical evidence indicates that building construction projects in Kenya have a low success rate of approximately 48% in terms of meeting scheduled time, cost, and quality targets, mainly due to inadequate coordination during the implementation of Mechanical Building Services (Muchungu, 2022). Furthermore, a substantial proportion of projects experience time overruns exceeding 50% and cost escalations above 20%, highlighting persistent inefficiencies within the sector (Ong'ondo et al., 2019).

Project Management Information System (PMIS) tools are intended to enhance project planning, coordination, monitoring, and control by integrating information, improving communication, and supporting informed decision-making. Despite their increasing adoption in the construction industry, their actual influence on the performance of Mechanical Building Services projects in Kenya remains unclear (Njau, 2019). The limited integration of PMIS has been associated with

inaccurate cost estimations, design coordination failures, duplication of tasks, and increased rework, all of which negatively affect project outcomes (Ong'ondo et al., 2019). However, there is insufficient empirical evidence specifically examining how PMIS tools impact the time, cost, quality, and overall performance of Mechanical Building Services in construction projects within Kiambu County.

Therefore, the research problem centers on the need to establish the relationship between Project Management Information System tools and the performance of Mechanical Building Services in construction projects in Kiambu County, Kenya. Addressing this gap is essential for determining whether PMIS adoption contributes significantly to improved coordination, efficiency, and project success, and for providing evidence-based recommendations to enhance project management practices in the local construction industry.

Objective

The study sought to assess the influence of project management information system tools and the performance of Mechanical Building Services in construction projects in Kiambu County, Kenya.

Theoretical Review

The Theory of Constraints (TOC), developed by Eliyahu M. Goldratt in the 1980s, provides a framework for identifying and managing bottlenecks that limit system performance (Mabin & Balderstone, 2020). Applied to Project Management Information Systems (PMIS), TOC helps project managers pinpoint constraints such as limited system functionality, inadequate user training, or integration issues with other tools (Mishra, 2020; Orouji, 2016). By focusing on these critical bottlenecks, managers can optimize system usage, improve data accuracy, and enhance decision-making processes (Sarkar et al., 2021). In construction projects, TOC facilitates better coordination of Mechanical Building Services by addressing inefficiencies, reducing rework, and improving stakeholder satisfaction, ultimately enhancing project performance.

TOC also highlights the importance of PMIS quality in identifying and addressing project constraints. High-quality PMIS tools help detect issues such as poor communication, inaccurate data, and workflow inefficiencies, enabling timely corrective actions. The system's information output status, when accurate and timely, allows managers to monitor risks, optimize resource allocation, and prevent delays, improving project outcomes. Additionally, the level of PMIS utilization directly impacts the ability to manage constraints, ensuring better decision-making, minimizing project downtime, and enhancing overall efficiency in Mechanical Building Services. PMIS software capabilities further support project success by streamlining planning, scheduling, monitoring, and reporting processes, allowing real-time detection and resolution of bottlenecks.

The Resource-Based Theory (RBT) emphasizes that a firm's competitive advantage is driven by unique and valuable resources (Rezakhani, 2017; Nathagopan et al., 2016). In the context of PMIS, resources such as skilled personnel, proprietary software, and robust data infrastructure can be leveraged to improve project outcomes (Govan & Damajanovic, 2016). High-quality PMIS acts as a VRIN (valuable, rare, inimitable, non-substitutable) resource that enables accurate data management, effective communication, and coordinated stakeholder engagement. By strategically deploying these resources, construction projects can enhance performance in Mechanical Building Services, achieving better time, cost, and quality outcomes.

RBT also underscores the strategic value of PMIS information output, utilization, and software capabilities. Timely and reliable PMIS information supports decision-making, risk management, and optimized resource allocation, improving efficiency and reducing waste. The degree of PMIS utilization reflects how well technological resources are exploited for project execution, influencing progress tracking, downtime reduction, and overall project efficiency. Advanced PMIS software functions as a technological asset that integrates planning, scheduling, monitoring, and reporting,

providing organizations with a sustainable competitive advantage and improving the execution of Mechanical Building Services tasks.

Systems Theory provides a holistic perspective, viewing construction projects as interconnected systems where stakeholders, resources, and tasks interact dynamically. Applying systems theory to PMIS highlights the importance of understanding these interdependencies to optimize project workflows and improve outcomes. High-quality PMIS serves as a central hub, ensuring smooth communication, real-time data sharing, and coordination across project components. Effective utilization of PMIS tools enhances collaboration, milestone tracking, and decision-making, while software capabilities integrate planning, scheduling, and resource management into a unified system. By addressing interactions and dependencies within the project, PMIS contributes to improved efficiency, reduced errors, and enhanced performance of Mechanical Building Services.

Conceptual Model and Hypothesis

Conceptual framework can be defined as a set of broad ideas and principles taken from relevant fields of inquiry and used to structure a subsequent presentation (Myers, 2013). Figure 1 show the conceptual framework which was used in this study and depicts the interrelationship between the study variables.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Empirical Review

Raymond and Bergeron (2015) examined the quality of Project Management Information System (PMIS) tools and their impact on project performance using a PMIS success model. The model

assessed five constructs: PMIS tool quality, information output quality, tool usage, individual impacts, and overall project success. Data collected from 39 project managers revealed that high-quality PMIS tools significantly contribute to effective project management. Specifically, improvements were observed in project planning, scheduling, monitoring, and control, leading to more timely and informed decision-making, and overall enhanced managerial efficiency.

Kaitare et al. (2016) investigated the influence of PMIS information output on construction project performance, focusing on Horizon Construction Company. Using a purposive sample of 86 respondents from a target population of 110, the study found that the quality of information generated by PMIS tools has a strong positive correlation with project performance. High-quality information enabled project managers to perform tasks more efficiently and professionally, improving decision-making and enhancing the overall outcomes of the construction projects.

Ngari (2016) explored how the level of PMIS tool utilization affects project performance in youth polytechnic development projects in Embu County, Kenya. The study sampled 10 managers, 43 instructors, and 27 support staff using simple random sampling techniques. Findings indicated that ease of use, accessibility, learnability, and system flexibility are critical for producing accurate, relevant, and secure project information. Higher levels of PMIS utilization were linked to better project monitoring, coordination, and overall project success, as users could effectively leverage system features for decision-making.

Ngari (2016) further assessed the influence of PMIS software capabilities on project performance in the same context. Using descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation analysis, the study established that PMIS software which generates high-quality, timely information enables project managers to perform their tasks more efficiently and professionally. Effective use of software functionalities improved planning, monitoring, and reporting processes, thereby increasing the probability of successful project outcomes. This emphasizes that both the capabilities of PMIS software and the way it is utilized are critical determinants of project performance.

Research Methodology

The study adopts a descriptive research design to investigate the impact of Project Management Information System (PMIS) tools on the performance of Mechanical Building Services in commercial building projects in Kiambu County, Kenya (Cooper, 2016; Kothari, 2014; Mangal & Mangal, 2017). The target population consists of 154 key project stakeholders—architects, engineers, project managers, and contractors—who interact directly with PMIS tools for planning, scheduling, budgeting, and coordination. A census approach is employed, with all 154 respondents administered structured questionnaires divided into sections covering demographic data, PMIS tool quality, information output, utilization levels, software capabilities, and project performance. Data collection is supplemented by a pilot study of 16 respondents (10% of the sample) to ensure reliability and validity, using Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha > 0.7$) for internal consistency and content, construct, internal, and external validity checks. Collected data will be cleaned, coded, and analyzed using SPSS version 24.0, employing descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means) and inferential statistics, including Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis. The regression model, $Y = \beta_0 + X_1\beta_1 + X_2\beta_2 + X_3\beta_3 + X_4\beta_4 + \mu$, will assess the simultaneous effects of PMIS tool quality, information output, utilization, and software ability on project performance, with significance tested at $p \leq 0.05$, providing a structured framework to evaluate how PMIS tools influence efficiency, cost control, and overall project outcomes.

Results and Discussion

Multivariate regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between independent variables (Quality of PMIS Tools, PMIS Tools' Information Output Status, Utilization Level of PMIS Tools and PMIS Tool Software Ability) and dependent variable (performance of mechanical building services in construction Projects in Kiambu County, Kenya).

Table 1. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.961	0.923	0.920	0.190

The model summary was used to explain the variation in the dependent variable that could be explained by the independent variables. The r-squared for the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable was 0.923. This implied that 92.3% of the variation in the dependent variable (performance of mechanical building services in construction Projects in Kiambu County, Kenya) could be explained by independent variables (Quality of PMIS Tools, PMIS Tools Information Output Status, Utilization Level of PMIS Tools and PMIS Tools Software Ability).

Table 2. Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of R Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	52.257	4	13.064	361.106	0.00
	Residual	4.378	121	0.036		
	Total	56.635	125			

The ANOVA was used to determine whether the model was a good fit for the data. F calculated was 361.106 and the p value was 0.000 less than 0.05, the model was considered as a good fit for the data. Henceforth, it can be used to predict the influence of Quality of PMIS tools, PMIS tools Information Output Status, Utilization Level of PMIS tools and PMIS tools Software ability on performance of mechanical building services in construction Projects in Kiambu County, Kenya.

Table 3 Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std.Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	.556	.102		5.445	.000
	Quality of PMIS Tools	.105	.074	.116	1.416	.001
	PMIS Tools Information Output Status	.175	.080	.195	2.197	.000
	Utilization Level of PMIS Tools	.454	.099	.498	4.585	.000
	PMIS Tools Software Ability	.356	.073	.396	4.852	.000

The regression model was as follows:

$$Y = 0.556 + 0.105X_1 + 0.175X_2 + 0.454X_3 + 0.356X_4$$

According to the results, Quality of PMIS tools was found to have a positive linearly significant influence on performance of mechanical building services in construction Projects in Kiambu County ($\beta=0.105$, p value = $0.01 < 0.05$). This means that one unit change in quality of PMIS tools while holding all other variables at zero results in 0.105 unit increase in performance of mechanical building services in construction Projects. Similarly, PMIS tools Information Output Status was found to have a positive linearly significant influence on performance of mechanical building services in construction Projects in Kiambu County ($\beta=0.175$, $p=0.00 < 0.05$). Here, holding all other variables at zero, one unit change in PMIS tools Information Output Status results in 0.175 unit increase in performance of mechanical building services in construction.

Utilization Level of PMIS tools was also found to have a positive linearly significant influence on performance of mechanical building services in construction ($\beta=0.454$, $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). Here, when all other predictor variables are held at zero, one unit change in project leadership skills results in 0.454 unit increase in performance of mechanical building services in construction Projects.

Finally, PMIS tools Software Ability was found to have a positive linearly significant influence on performance of Orange Money ($\beta=0.356$, $p=0.00 < 0.05$). This means that one unit change in stakeholder's participation results in 0.356 unit increase in performance of mechanical building services in construction in Kiambu County, Kenya. The beta coefficients indicate the relative importance of each independent variable (Quality of PMIS tools, PMIS tools Information Output Status, Utilization Level of PMIS tools and PMIS tools Software Ability) in influencing the dependent variable (performance of mechanical building services in construction Projects in Kiambu County, Kenya). Utilization Level of PMIS tools is the most important variable in influencing performance of mechanical building services in construction Projects ($\beta=0.454$), followed by PMIS tools Software Ability ($\beta=0.356$), then PMIS Information Output Status ($\beta=0.175$) and the least is Quality of PMIS tools ($\beta=0.105$).

Conclusion

The study concludes that Project Management Information System (PMIS) tools significantly influence the performance of Mechanical Building Services in construction projects in Kiambu County, Kenya. Findings indicate a positive relationship between the quality of PMIS tools and project performance, as well as a positive relationship between PMIS information output status and performance outcomes. The results further reveal a very strong relationship between the utilization level of PMIS tools and project performance, highlighting the importance of effective system use. Additionally, there is a very strong association between the ability of PMIS tools software, particularly BIM, and the performance of Mechanical Building Services. Overall, the study establishes that PMIS tool quality, utilization levels, information output status, and software capability collectively contribute to improved time, cost, and quality performance in construction projects in Kenya.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, it is recommended that project stakeholders in Kenya's construction industry prioritize the adoption and effective implementation of standardized and high-quality Project Management Information System (PMIS) tools to enhance the performance of Mechanical Building Services. Emphasis should be placed on selecting PMIS platforms that support efficient communication, accurate project data management, and real-time monitoring to improve execution quality. Stakeholders should also promote higher utilization levels of PMIS by ensuring that project teams conduct design, coordination, and communication activities through a centralized system, thereby strengthening progress tracking and reducing downtime. Additionally, organizations should invest in PMIS software with robust capabilities in planning, scheduling, monitoring, and reporting to align with specific project requirements. Finally, PMIS tools should incorporate real-time, centralized information output and reporting features to enhance timely decision-making, coordination, and overall project performance in mechanical building services.

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